

Chelatometric titration of iron, zinc and aluminium involving masking and demasking with acetylacetone

J. K. Mondal, S. Basak, S. S. Mukherjee and Dipali Kundu*

Analytical Chemistry Division, Central Glass & Ceramic Research Institute, Kolkata-700 032, India

E-mail : dipali_kundu@hotmail.com

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A stepwise complexometric method with EDTA has been developed for the determination of iron, zinc and aluminium in a single aliquot solution involving direct titration of iron(III)-acetylacetonate at pH 3.0 using acetylacetone as an auto-indicator. Zinc is determined in the same solution by direct titration with EDTA raising pH to 5.3 using xylenol orange as indicator, while aluminium being masked with acetylacetone at room temperature ($25 \pm 5^\circ$). However, aluminium is determined in the same solution indirectly with EDTA at pH 5.3 using xylenol orange as indicator after demasking aluminium from aluminium acetylacetonate at 90° and formation of Al-EDTA complex. Alternatively, aluminium may be determined by adding NaF and titrating released EDTA with zinc acetate solution. Interferences due to titanium, zirconium, manganese, nickel, cobalt, copper and chromium have been eliminated by complexing them with different ligands. The method has been standardised against synthetic solutions and applied to various enamel and frit samples.

Direct titration of iron, zinc and aluminium with ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA) in the presence of one another has been an analytical problem for long, although different procedures^{1,2} have been reported for the complexometric determination of iron, zinc and aluminium separately with EDTA. Ghosh *et al.*³ determined iron and aluminium simultaneously at pH 2.0 using sulfosalicylic acid and EDTA for iron and DCTA for aluminium. Zinc was determined with EDTA in the presence of iron after separation of the latter as hydroxide⁴. Fritz *et al.*⁵ determined zinc with EDTA in the presence of aluminium at pH 7 after masking aluminium with acetylacetone but aluminium was not determined at the same time. Thus, no method has so far been reported for the stepwise determination of iron, zinc and aluminium in a single aliquot solution without prior separation.

The present communication deals with the development of a method for the stepwise determination of iron, zinc and aluminium with EDTA in a single aliquot solution after masking and demasking of iron and aluminium with acetylacetone at different pH and temperature. The method has been applied for their determination in enamel and frit samples.

Results and Discussion

It is known⁶ that Fe^{III} forms a stable complex with acetylacetone $\text{Fe}(\text{acac})_3$ whose formation constant⁷ is 23.87 at 25° . However, $\text{Fe}(\text{acac})_3$ is unstable⁸ and being pH and temperature dependent, the titration with EDTA is possible.

In order to determine the optimum pH for the quantitative formation of $\text{Fe}(\text{acac})_3$ as well as its titration with EDTA, a series of experiments were performed with known concentration of iron and acetylacetone by varying pH of the solution from 0 to 5.0. The results indicate that the complexation of iron at $25 \pm 5^\circ$ with acetylacetone is quantitative in the pH range 2.0–3.0.

In the titration of zinc with EDTA, aluminium interferes seriously¹ because the values of formation constants of EDTA complexes of these two elements are very close ($\log K_{\text{Zn-EDTA}} = 16.20$, $\log K_{\text{Al-EDTA}} = 16.13$). In order to titrate zinc with EDTA, separation or masking of aluminium is necessary¹. Fritz *et al.*⁵ titrated zinc at pH 7.0 after masking aluminium with acetylacetone. It has been observed that $\text{Al}(\text{acac})_3$ complex is stable at room temperature ($25 \pm 5^\circ$) and it dissociates slowly only on standing for few hours or on increasing the temperature. Thus, in the presence of aluminium, zinc was first titrated with EDTA at pH 5.3 after masking aluminium with acetylacetone. Next, $\text{Al}(\text{acac})_3$ is allowed to dissociate and to form a more stable complex with EDTA at the same pH.

The demasking of acetylacetone from $\text{Al}(\text{acac})_3$ by EDTA proceeds very slowly at room temperature ($25 \pm 5^\circ$) and requires too long a time (about 24 h) for the complete dissociation of $\text{Al}(\text{acac})_3$ complex. However, the rate of reaction is found to be rapid on increasing the temperature and time. Therefore, a series of experiments were conducted to establish the time-temperature relationship for quantitative release of aluminium from its acetylacetonate

complex and formation of the Al-EDTA complex at pH 5.3.

It is evident from Fig.1 that aluminium is not released from its acetylacetonate complex within 50 mins at 20° (curve A) even in the presence of an excess of EDTA. However, Al(acac)₃ complex gradually decomposes with the increase in temperature and time at the same pH (curves B to D). The released aluminium immediately forms complex with EDTA. It can be seen (curve E) that a minimum time of 10 min is necessary for quantitative release (i.e. 100% recovery) of aluminium at 90°.

Fig. 1. Effect of time on the quantitative release of aluminium from Al(acac)₃ at different temperatures : (A) 20°, (B) 40°, (C) 50°, (D) 70°, (E) 90°; the broken line represents the amount of Al taken; [Al] = 8.20 mg ml⁻¹, [Hacac] = 1.0% (v/v), pH = 5.3.

Quantitative determination of zinc and aluminium are also dependent on the amount of acetylacetonate to be added. Since acetylacetonate acts as a masking agent for aluminium, its concentration plays a significant role in the determination of zinc. In order to optimise the concentration of acetylacetonate, a series of experiments were carried out with known concentrations of zinc and aluminium. It was found that low concentrations (<0.5%, v/v) of acetylacetonate give erroneous results of zinc and aluminium. This is probably due to the fact that at low acetylacetonate concentration, masking of aluminium is incomplete. This causes drifting at the end-point of zinc titration and gives higher values for zinc. Higher acetylacetonate concentrations (>1.0%, v/v) also give erroneous results for aluminium. This is probably due to the fact that at higher acetylacetonate concentration demasking of aluminium from its acetylacetonate complex is incomplete thereby giving low result for aluminium. The optimum concentration of acetylacetonate was found to be 0.5 to 1.0%, v/v.

The effect of foreign ions on the determination of iron, zinc and aluminium was studied. Interference of Ti⁴⁺ is eliminated by tartaric acid and that of Zr⁴⁺ and Mn²⁺ by citric acid. Cu²⁺ is masked with thiourea. Ni²⁺ and Co²⁺ are first masked with acetylacetonate and after titration of zinc their interferences are completely removed by KCN. Anions such as phosphate, fluoride, borate and sulfate have no effect.

The results for the determination of iron, zinc and aluminium in synthetic solution were found satisfactory.

The method was also successfully applied for the determination of iron, zinc and aluminium in multicomponent glass (NIST SRM 1412), borosilicate glass (NIST SRM 1411), enamel and frit samples and the results are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Determination of iron, zinc and aluminium in enamel and frit samples

Sample	Present (%)	Found (%) ^a	% Error
NIST SRM 1412			
Multicomponent glass :			
Fe ₂ O ₃	0.03 + 2.00 (added)	2.03	0.00
ZnO	4.48	4.49	0.22
Al ₂ O ₃	7.52	7.51	0.13
NIST SRM 1411			
Soft borosilicate glass :			
Fe ₂ O ₃	0.05 + 2.00 (added)	2.05	0.00
ZnO	3.85	3.86	0.26
Al ₂ O ₃	5.68	5.69	0.18
Enamel :			
Fe ₂ O ₃	1.22	1.22	0.00
ZnO	0.71 + 2.00 (added)	2.72	0.37
Al ₂ O ₃	3.82	3.81	0.26
Frit :			
Fe ₂ O ₃	0.15 + 2.00 (added)	2.15	0.00
ZnO	8.44	8.43	0.12
Al ₂ O ₃	10.75	10.76	0.09

^aMean of three determinations.

Experimental

All the reagents used were of A.R. grade. Double-distilled water was used for preparation of all the solutions.

Solutions of iron (1.40 mg ml⁻¹), zinc (1.64 mg ml⁻¹) and aluminium (0.675 mg ml⁻¹) were prepared from the metals. Buffer solutions of pH 5.3 and 3.0 were prepared by mixing sodium acetate and glacial acetic acid. Solutions of 0.025 mol dm⁻³ Na₂EDTA and 0.025 mol dm⁻³ zinc acetate were prepared and standardised. Xylenol orange (0.01 %, w/v) and methyl orange (0.03%, w/v) solutions were prepared in water.

Procedure : Solutions (1–10 ml) of iron, zinc and aluminium containing 1.40–14.00 mg of Fe, 1.64–16.40 mg of Zn and 0.675–6.75 mg of Al were transferred separately, neutralised with aqueous ammonia (1 : 1), then acidified with a few drops of HCl (1 : 1), followed by addition of buffer solution (pH 3.0, 20 ml) and acetylacetonate (99.5%, 1 ml) and the total volume was adjusted to 100 ml with water. The solution was titrated at room temperature with EDTA to a colourless end-point. The solution was neutralised with ammonia (1 : 1) using methyl orange as indicator, acidified with a few drops of HCl (1 : 1), then buffer solution (pH 5.3, 20 ml) and xylenol orange indicator were added to it and titrated with EDTA to yellow end-point. The solution was heated to 90° for 5 min, excess EDTA solution added, boiled and cooled to room temperature. Then buffer solution (pH 5.3; 10 ml) was added and titrated with standard zinc acetate solution in presence of xylenol orange indicator to pink end-point.

Determination of Fe, Zn and Al in enamels and frits :

The dried (110°) sample (0.5 g) was taken in PTFE basin and moisten with 5–6 drops of water, followed by addition of sulfuric acid (1 : 1; 10 ml) and hydrofluoric acid (20 ml). The basin was heated on a sand-bath till fumes of sulfur trioxide evolved copiously. The basin was cooled and its inner side was washed with water. HF (10 ml) was added and the process was repeated. Then water (150 ml) was added and boiled on a hot-plate. It was cooled and set aside overnight. The solution was filtered to separate precipitate if any. The filtrate and washing was made up to 250 ml with water and used for titration.

Calculation :

$$\text{Amount of Fe (\%)} = \frac{A B}{W} \times 100$$

$$\text{Amount of Zn (\%)} = \frac{C D}{W} \times 100$$

$$\text{Amount of Al (\%)} = \frac{(E-F) G}{W} \times 100$$

where, *A* is the volume (ml) of EDTA required at pH 3.0, *B* the equivalent Fe (g ml⁻¹) of EDTA, *C* the volume (ml) of EDTA required at pH 5.3, *D* the equivalent Zn (g ml⁻¹) of EDTA, (*E-F*) the [volume (ml) of zinc acetate solution required for blank EDTA] – [volume (ml) of zinc acetate solution required for excess EDTA], *G* the equivalent Al (g ml⁻¹) of zinc acetate solution, and *W* the weight (g) of sample in the aliquot solution taken.

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